

The Role of Interaction Rate in Classical and Statistical Mechanics

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In statistical mechanics, the entropy, written as a function of $f(e_i)$, the particle number distribution, is maximized with respect to the distribution, subject to constraints on energy and particle number. This is often described as maximizing arrangements in phase space and the result yields an explicit expression for the distribution. In previous notes, we have, however, shown that one may obtain distributions by considering a reaction balance together with conservation of energy. The distribution $f(e)$ appears in reaction equations where it plays the role of governing the rate of the reaction. For equilibrium, a balance in various reactions is necessary, so the distribution $f(e)$ must adjust to satisfy this requirement. Thus, one may think of equilibrium as being related to adjusting reaction rates. The entropy is a special expression which when maximized yields the equilibrium distribution. It is like a rate balancing expression. One may argue that changing rates slightly does not change equilibrium to first order, but a second view is that an equilibrium solution does not give extra information to the entropy function when rates are changed. For example, changing $f(e_i)$ means that the rate of reaction of particles with e_i increases, thus information is introduced into the system. For an equilibrium solution in the entropy, no new information is obtained to first order when a fluctuation is introduced.

In classical mechanics, one may either start with Newton's second law, or energy conservation: $\text{Kinetic energy}(x) + V(x) = E$. Thus, at first glance there does not seem to be any link with statistical mechanics. In classical mechanics, however, there is a reaction with $V(x)$ and also a rate at each x given by $v(x)$ or $v(t), x(t)$. If one changes $x(t)$ (and so $v(t)$), i.e. increases it in places and decreases it in others, one no longer has the "equilibrium solution". In other words, it seems there should be a function like entropy, which may be used with constraints if necessary, to obtain the "equilibrium" rate i.e. $v(t)$ which is obtainable from $x(t)$. We try to argue that the Lagrangian plays this role.

In statistical mechanics, one may obtain entropy by writing a reaction balance equation in terms of reaction rate which is linked to conservation of energy. For classical mechanics, we argue one links the rate with the conservation of energy equation in order to find the function (Lagrangian) which when maximized, yields the "equilibrium" rate. Thus, we speculate that the Lagrangian approach in classical mechanics and the maximization of entropy in statistical mechanics are of the same nature.

Statistical Mechanics

In statistical mechanics, one often speaks of maximizing phase space in order to obtain $f(e)$, the particle distribution. Thus, factorial expressions may be written and the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions obtained. In such a scenario, one does not think of reaction rates, but rather of a somewhat static picture of arrangements. Physically, however,

reactions or interactions occur and these create the equilibrium distribution. One may obtain the above distributions simply from reaction balance linked to energy conservation in each reaction. The reaction equations are really a balance of reaction rates because the amount of $f(e_i)$ for a particular e_i drives the reaction. Thus, it seems it is the rates which must be balanced.

For all cases: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. For the MB case: $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and for the FD and BE cases: $f(e_1) [1 -/+ f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1 -/+ f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1 -/+ f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1 -/+ f(e_2)]$. ((1))

If one takes \ln of the rate equations and links them to the conservation of energy equation, one obtains the distributions in question i.e.:

$$\text{MB } \ln(f(e_i)) = (e_i - u)/T \quad \text{FD } \ln[f(e_i)/(1-f(e_i))] = (e_i - u)/T \quad \text{BE } \ln[f(e_i)/(f(e_i)+1)] = (e_i - u)/T \quad ((2))$$

Kaniadakis (1) argues that for generalized kinematics one may use:

$$\ln(k(f(e_i))) = (e_i - u)/T \quad ((3)) \quad \text{For the MB case, } k=1.$$

One may next integrate $\ln(k(f(e_i)))$ over df to obtain a Kaniadakis entropy. Varying this with respect to f i.e. d/df and using energy and particle number constraints yields ((3)) back again, as expected.

We argue in this note that by varying $f(e_i)$, one varies the reaction rate. Thus, one starts with two equations, the first related to reaction rate balance and the second to conservation of energy. From these, one constructs a function which when varied with respect to the rate (subject to constraints) reaches a maximum. In other words, varying the rate slightly does not change the function. This seems to be linked to the idea of an equilibrium solution. In a system at equilibrium, there are small fluctuations in $f(e_i)$ which change rates. These, however, should not destroy the equilibrium, otherwise it is not stable. Thus, the mathematical idea seems to be that small changes in $f(e_i)$ (i.e. the reaction rates) to a "special function of $f(e_i)$ " leave the function unchanged if one uses the equilibrium $f(e_i)$.

We try to argue in this note, that this same reasoning applies to classical mechanics.

Classical Mechanics

Classical mechanics of a single particle may be written in terms of Newton's second law or conservation of energy $KE(x) + V(x) = E$. Thus, nothing needs to be maximized and one has a deterministic theory yielding $x(t)$ for each t . By differentiating with respect to t , one obtains velocity and acceleration. Nevertheless, in classical mechanics there is a reaction between the particle and $V(x)$ and a reaction rate given by $v(x)$. To see this, consider a tiny interval dx . Regardless of $v(x)$, the particle receives $V(x) dx$ amount of energy when passing through dx . The time to pass through dx , however, depends on $v(x)$. Thus, the reaction rate changes with $v(x)$. The reaction rate may also be thought of in terms of varying the function $x(t)$ i.e. $x(t) + \delta x(t)$. By differentiating with respect to t one obtains velocity. Thus, the idea of classical

mechanics seems to be to find the correct $x(t)$. Can this be done using variational ideas? The Lagrangian approach is one such way of using variation subject to constraints to obtain classical kinematical equations. Is this approach at all linked to that of varying entropy in statistical mechanics? We try to argue in this note that there may be a connection.

To make this connection, we argue that one must consider the reaction rate i.e. $v(t)$ and energy conservation in classical mechanics as reaction rate and energy conservation are the two key features in statistical mechanics used to create the Kaniadakis entropy. For classical mechanics, the reaction rate $v(t)$ is linked to $x(t)$, thus changing the functional form of $x(t)$ changes that of $v(t)$. The energy conservation equation is: $KE(x)+V(x)=E$.

The argument seems to be that there should be a function of $x(t)$, $v(t)$ in classical mechanics (i.e. related to the rate) such that if one varies the functional form of $x(t)$ (and hence the functional form of $v(t)$), subject to constraints (if any) one obtains 0. Such an $x(t)$ is then the equilibrium solution. The energy conservation equation should play a role in determining this function. One might think of $\delta x(t)$, the tiny functional deviation, as being a fluctuation to a classical system. Such a fluctuation is not contained directly in Newton's law or the conservation of energy equation because these assume no fluctuations. In nature, however, such fluctuations may occur, it seems, even in classical mechanics. The idea seems to be that such tiny fluctuations or perturbations should not destroy the overall equilibrium solution, at least to first order. This seems to be similar to a particle at the bottom of a parabola which is given a perturbation. The overall equilibrium position at the bottom of the parabola is not destroyed, but there is a small perturbative motion added.

How is this related to statistical mechanics? It was noted that statistical mechanics maximizes arrangements in phase space. This seems to be equivalent to maximizing uncertainty. In classical mechanics, if one perturbs $v(t)$, it is either too fast or too slow and so one knows how it has to be adjusted, i.e. how the reaction rate needs to be adjusted to return to equilibrium. Thus, one has "information". Consider the analogy in statistical mechanics in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. If one increase $f(e_i)$ for a certain e_i , one has an excess of particles with this energy and their rate of reaction increases. This increase then lowers $f(e_i)$. Thus, one has "information". At equilibrium, there is a loss of information. Given the reaction of two particles e_1 and e_2 , one only knows that the final two particles' energies must sum to e_1+e_2 . (There is momentum conservation in the picture as well.)

Creation of the Lagrangian

The last step seems to be to create the function which when varied with respect to $x(t)$, $v(t)$ yields zero. This function should be linked to the reaction rate and energy conservation if the analogy with statistical mechanics holds. The idea is that $x(t)$ changes to a different function $x(t)+\delta x(t)$, forcing a change in $v(t)$ i.e. $v(t)+\delta v(t) = d/dt x(t) + d/dt \delta x(t)$. This leads to change in the interaction rate (due to the change in $v(t)$) and in the value of the interaction in $V(x)$ i.e. $V(x+\delta x)$ due to $x+\delta x$. Thus, two considerations come into play, it seems. Using

conservation of energy, a change in $V(x)$ should be balanced by one in kinetic energy. The kinetic energy, however, changes due to $v(t) + d/dt \delta x(t)$ i.e.

$.5m (v + \delta v)^2 = .5mv^2 + m v d/dt \delta x$ to first approximation.

Thus, one needs to perform an integration by parts to change $d/dt \delta x$ into δx which yields a sign change or: $-d/dt dKE/dv$. This must match the change $dV/dx \delta x$ for energy to be conserved. A Lagrange multiplier is not used to account for energy conservation as in statistical mechanics. As a result of the sign change, it seems that $L=KE- V$ is the function to be altered with respect to $x(t)$, $v(t)$ etc. The maximization of this function (subject to constraints if any) should yield the equilibrium solution.

Thus, the Lagrangian L seems to play an analogous role to entropy, although for entropy maximization, one adds a particle number and energy conservation constraint. For the Lagrangian, an energy conservation constraint is not necessary because one already considers a change in $V(x)$ as balancing one in $KE(x)$. The particle number is also not changing because there is only one particle and it has one $v(x)$ value at each x .

As an aside, even if one did not know Newton's second law, one may reason that $v(t) = v(x(t))$. Then, $dv/dt = \text{full time derivative} = dv/dx v = G(x)$ or $G(x) dx = v dv$. Integrating yields $v^2/2 = \int G(x) dx$. Mass does not enter the picture in this argument, but otherwise one begins to see the idea of a creation of a kinetic energy due to a kind of work in the system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that there is a common strategy used in finding $f(e)$ the particle distribution in statistical mechanics and $v(t)$, $x(t)$ in classical mechanics in the Lagrangian approach. The strategy, it seems, is to consider rates of reactions together with conservation of energy. In statistical mechanics, the reaction rate is related to $f(e_i)$ and one imposes conservation of energy in a reaction for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases. Changing $f(e_i)$ for a particular e_i , changing the rate of reaction for particles with e_i introduces "information" into the system, i.e. there is a preference for e_i to react. To obtain entropy i.e. a function whose derivative with respect to the reaction rate yields 0 subject to energy and particle number constraints, one may integrate $\ln(k(f(e_i)))$ over df as suggested by Kaniadakis (1). $\ln(k(f(e_i))) = (e_i - u)/T$ emerges from the combination of the reaction rate with energy conservation. Integration over df is the opposite operation as d/df , so one obtains the original result back. The idea seems to be that there is a function of $f(e_i)$, namely the entropy, which when varied slightly from the equilibrium $f(e_i)$, i.e. the equilibrium rates of reaction, subject to constraints, yields 0 to first order. Thus, small changes to the functional form of $f(e_i)$ do not disrupt equilibrium up to first order.

This is not a new idea, it exists in classical mechanics. For example, a particle in stable equilibrium may oscillate about this equilibrium if slightly perturbed. We argue that in classical mechanics $v(t)$ is the reaction rate as a particle reacts with $V(x)$. Thus, changing the functional form of $x(t)$ to $x(t) + \delta x(t)$ and $v(t)$ to $d/dt x(t) + d/dt \delta x(t)$ represents a perturbation. One

wishes to conserve energy while making such a change and so applies the conservation of energy equation. Finally, one needs a function which does not change to first order subject to a change $\delta x(t)$. This yields the Lagrangian $=KE(x)-V(x)$, obtained largely from the conservation of energy equation. It plays the analogous role as entropy in statistical mechanics (although one usually adds an energy and particle constraint instead of incorporating them as in the case of the Lagrangian). The idea of “information” loss, however, seems to be the same in both cases. In statistical mechanics, if $f(e_i)$ is increased from equilibrium, there will be increased numbers of reactions of e_i particles. This is “extra information”. In classical mechanics, if $v(t)$ decreases from equilibrium at point x , the rate of reaction slows down at this point, and this is extra information. It needs to be sped up. Thus, changes from equilibrium yield information about changes to reaction rates and also information about how the system must adjust to change the deviation. A maximum is desired because it not only means there is no motion away from equilibrium to first order, but also that one does not require information about how the system’s reaction to the fluctuation. Thus, we argue there is a statistical sense i.e. loss of information, in both classical and statistical mechanics.

References

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